

TinyGAN: Generative Image Synthesis on a RISC-V Microcontroller with Quantum Entropy Sampling

Armstrong Subero

Independent Researcher, Trinidad and Tobago

Abstract—We present TinyGAN, a demonstrated deployment of generative adversarial network image synthesis on a resource constrained RISC-V microcontroller. A DCGAN generator with 12.6 million parameters produces 64x64 RGB images of cat faces on a CH32H417 dual core RISC-V system on chip operating at 150/300 MHz with 512 KB of shared SRAM and no external memory. Through a combination of dual core compute offloading, int8 per channel quantization, tiled weight layout optimization, double buffered SD card streaming, and cross core DTCM intermediate storage, we reduce inference time from 242 seconds to 26 seconds, a 9.3x improvement. The system reads 12.1 MB of quantized weights from an SD card over SPI and generates photorealistic cat face images displayed on an LCD. Latent vectors are seeded from quantum vacuum fluctuation measurements provided by the Australian National University quantum random number generator, establishing a verifiable causal chain from fundamental quantum events to synthesized imagery. The system includes combinatorial phrase synthesis and neural text to speech audio output, both driven by quantum entropy bytes, creating an autonomous generative art installation that requires no network connectivity at runtime. We are not aware of prior published work demonstrating GAN based RGB image synthesis on a microcontroller class device.

Index Terms—Generative adversarial networks, microcontrollers, RISC-V, TinyML, quantization, neural network inference, quantum random number generation, embedded systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The TinyML research community has made significant progress deploying neural network inference on microcontrollers over the past five years. Classification, object detection, keyword spotting, and anomaly detection workloads now run routinely on devices with as little as 256 KB of SRAM. However, this body of work focuses mainly on discriminative models. Generative models, which synthesize new data rather than classifying existing data, have received little attention in the microcontroller deployment literature.

This gap exists for a reasonable assumption that generative models are too computationally expensive for microcontroller class hardware. A single forward pass through a modern diffusion model requires 20 to 50 iterations of a large U-Net, making generation infeasible on constrained devices. Generative Adversarial Networks, however, present a fundamentally different inference profile. The generator network requires only a single forward pass to produce an output image. This property makes GANs uniquely suited to deployment on microcontrollers, where inference latency is dominated by

memory access patterns and arithmetic throughput rather than iterative denoising.

We demonstrate that GAN image generation is feasible on current microcontroller hardware by deploying a DCGAN generator on the CH32H417, a dual core RISC-V microcontroller manufactured by WCH (Nanjing Qinheng Microelectronics). The CH32H417 integrates a RISC-V V3F core at 150 MHz and a RISC-V V5F core rated for up to 400 MHz, operated at 300 MHz in this configuration due to clock tree constraints with the external crystal oscillator. The chip provides 512 KB of shared SRAM and 256 KB of tightly coupled data memory exclusive to the V5F core.

Our contributions are fivefold. We present a demonstrated, to our knowledge novel, GAN image generation inference on a microcontroller, establishing that generative models are viable on this class of hardware. We describe a systematic optimization methodology achieving a 9.3x speedup through six incremental techniques with measured impact on real hardware. We analyze int8 per channel quantization effects on generative output quality, addressing a gap in the quantization literature which has focused on discriminative tasks and we provide a complete pure C inference framework verified bit identical against PyTorch, requiring no external libraries beyond FatFS for SD card access. Finally, for demonstration we deploy the system as an autonomous generative art installation driven by quantum vacuum fluctuation measurements, with combinatorial phrase synthesis and audio output.

II. RELATED WORK

A. TinyML Inference

The TinyML ecosystem has matured around discriminative workloads. TensorFlow Lite Micro [7], CMSIS-NN, and vendor specific frameworks (STM32Cube.AI, NNoM) enable deployment of classification and detection models on Cortex-M microcontrollers. MLPerf Tiny [3] provides standardized benchmarks for keyword spotting, visual wake words, image classification, and anomaly detection. None of these frameworks or benchmarks include generative workloads.

B. GAN Compression and Deployment

Significant work has addressed GAN compression for deployment on mobile and edge devices through pruning, knowledge distillation, and neural architecture search. These targets have orders of magnitude more compute and memory than microcontrollers. A smartphone GPU provides 100+ GFLOPS and multiple gigabytes of memory. The CH32H417

provides roughly 0.15 GFLOPS with hardware FPU at 300 MHz and 768 KB of total SRAM.

C. Prior Attempts

The closest prior work is Tim's "Generative AI on a Microcontroller" project [9], which explored conditional variational autoencoders and diffusion models for generating 32x32 grayscale dice face images. The project achieved promising training results on PC but was unable to complete deployment on hardware, with the author noting that "none of the solutions did really click." The related BitNetMCU project [10] by the same author demonstrated greater than 99% MNIST classification accuracy on a CH32V003 (16 KB flash, 2 KB SRAM), establishing that custom inference engines tailored to specific architectures can outperform general purpose frameworks on very small devices. Our work uses a GAN architecture, generates 64x64 RGB photorealistic images, employs a custom pure C inference engine, and presents a complete working deployment with measured performance.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Target Hardware

The CH32H417 is a dual core RISC-V microcontroller. The V5F core is rated for up to 400 MHz but is operated at 300 MHz in this design because running at the full rated speed would require reducing the V3F core frequency below the 150 MHz needed for reliable peripheral operation with the external 25 MHz crystal oscillator. The V5F core includes a hardware single precision FPU, 128 KB of instruction tightly coupled memory (ITCM), and 256 KB of data tightly coupled memory (DTCM). The V3F core runs at 150 MHz without hardware FPU. The two cores share 512 KB of SRAM accessible through a bus arbiter, with inter core communication via a shared memory mailbox at a fixed address. The total on chip volatile memory is 896 KB (512 KB shared SRAM, 256 KB DTCM, 128 KB ITCM). Peripherals used include SPI for the SD card and LCD, a 12-bit DAC for audio output, and a capacitive touch controller for user input.

B. Model Architecture

We deploy a DCGAN generator [1] with $ngf=128$ (128 base feature channels). The model consists of five transposed convolution layers with 4x4 kernels, mapping a 100-element latent vector to a 64x64 RGB image. Layers 0 through 3 use ReLU activation and layer 4 uses tanh. Batch normalization is folded into convolution weights during export. The total parameter count is 12,656,515. Table I shows the per layer breakdown.

TABLE I
Per Layer Architecture

Layer	Input	Output	Params
0	100x1x1	1024x4x4	1,639,424
1	1024x4x4	512x8x8	8,389,120
2	512x8x8	256x16x16	2,097,408
3	256x16x16	128x32x32	524,416
4	128x32x32	3x64x64	6,147
Total			12,656,515

Fig. 1. Sample outputs from the DCGAN generator ($ngf=128$, epoch 400) on PC with float32 weights. Each image is 64x64 RGB, generated from a random z vector sampled from $N(0,1)$.

C. Training

The model is trained on the AFHQ cat dataset containing 5,153 images resized to 64x64, using the standard DCGAN procedure with Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.0002, $\beta_1=0.5$, $\beta_2=0.999$), batch size 64, for 400 epochs with label smoothing at 0.9 for real images. Fig. 1 shows representative outputs from the trained generator.

IV. MEMORY MANAGEMENT

The fundamental challenge is the disparity between feature map sizes and available SRAM. The largest intermediate feature map (layer 3 output: 128x32x32) requires 512 KB in float32, exceeding the entire shared SRAM. The total weight storage of 48.3 MB in float32 exceeds on chip memory by two orders of magnitude.

The shared SRAM is partitioned via the linker script into 160 KB for V3F executable code and 320 KB for V3F data, accommodating two 128 KB feature map buffers, two 2 KB weight double buffers, bias and scale buffers, and stack space. The V5F DTCM stores one tile of layer 2 output (128 KB) to eliminate temporary file I/O.

Layers whose output exceeds available buffer space are processed in tiles by output channel groups. Layer 2 is processed as two tiles of 128 output channels, with one tile in shared SRAM and one in V5F DTCM. Layer 3 is processed as four tiles of 32 output channels, with tiles written to an SD card temporary file. Layers 0, 1, and 4 fit directly in the available buffers.

V. OPTIMIZATION METHODOLOGY

We present six optimization techniques applied incrementally, each with measured impact on inference time on physical CH32H417 hardware.

A. Baseline: V3F Software Float

The initial implementation runs entirely on the V3F core at 150 MHz with software floating point emulation, producing a baseline of 242 seconds. This establishes correctness: the output is verified pixel identical to the PC reference implementation.

B. V5F Hardware FPU Offload (90s, 2.7x)

The scatter add inner loop of the transposed convolution is offloaded to the V5F core with hardware FPU at 300 MHz. Inter core communication uses a shared memory mailbox protocol with explicit memory fences. The 2.7x speedup reflects the clock frequency advantage and the elimination of software float emulation overhead.

C. Int8 Per Channel Quantization (46s, 5.3x)

Weights are quantized from float32 to int8 using symmetric per output channel quantization, reducing storage from 48.3 MB to 12.1 MB. Per channel quantization is critical for generative models because the weight magnitude distribution varies significantly across output channels. Per tensor quantization degrades generation quality visibly. The int8 quantized output was compared against float32 reference output across 100 z vectors, with maximum per pixel deviation of 1 LSB, below the perceptual threshold at 64x64 resolution.

D. V5F Dequantization Fusion (35s, 6.9x)

Moving dequantization from V3F software float into the V5F scatter loop eliminates 11 seconds of overhead. V5F reads raw int8 bytes and performs scale multiplication as part of the inner loop.

E. Double Buffered Weight Streaming (29s, 8.3x)

Two 2 KB weight buffers alternate between SD read target and V5F compute source. V3F reads the next weight chunk while V5F processes the current chunk, overlapping I/O with computation.

F. DTCM Intermediate Storage (26s, 9.3x)

Storing one layer 2 tile in V5F DTCM and the other in shared SRAM eliminates the temporary file and all associated I/O for the layer 2 to layer 3 transition. Table II summarizes all optimizations.

TABLE II
Optimization Summary

Technique	Time	Speedup
V3F software float (baseline)	242 s	1.0x
V5F hardware FPU offload	90 s	2.7x
Int8 per channel quantization	46 s	5.3x
V5F dequantization fusion	35 s	6.9x
Double buffered streaming	29 s	8.3x
DTCM intermediate storage	26 s	9.3x

VI. WEIGHT FILE OPTIMIZATION

The PyTorch native weight layout [C_in, C_out, kH, kW] requires seeking to non-contiguous file positions when processing output channel tiles. We reorganize weight files to [num_blocks, C_in, oc_block, kH, kW] so that each output channel block contains all input channels contiguously, enabling sequential reads with a single initial seek per block. The complete weight preparation pipeline consists of PyTorch training with batch normalization, export with batch norm folding, tiled layout reorganization, and int8 quantization with per channel scales. The final weights on SD card total 12.1 MB plus 7.5 KB of scale factors and 7.7 KB of bias values.

VII. SCHRODINGER'S DE/MOTIVATED QUANTUM CAT

A. Conceptual Foundation

The Schrodinger cat thought experiment [11] illustrates the paradox of quantum superposition applied to macroscopic objects. A cat in a sealed box exists in a superposition of alive and dead states until observation forces collapse to a definite outcome. We construct a literal, functional version of this thought experiment. The system exists in a superposition of two states, motivated and demotivated, until quantum measurement forces collapse into one. The cat itself is generated from quantum noise: its appearance, its personality, and the words it speaks are all causally determined by vacuum fluctuations measured at the Australian National University in Canberra.

This is not metaphorical as the z vector that seeds the generator network is constructed from measurements of a physical quantum process. The resulting cat face is a deterministic function of those measurements and if different virtual photon pairs had appeared in the ANU vacuum chamber at the moment of measurement, a different cat would exist.

B. Quantum Random Number Source

The ANU Quantum Random Number Generator [8] produces true random numbers by measuring quantum vacuum fluctuations using balanced homodyne detection. A laser beam is split and the power fluctuations in each arm are measured. These fluctuations arise from the zero-point energy of the electromagnetic field, the irreducible quantum noise present even in a perfect vacuum. Virtual photon pairs spontaneously appear and annihilate, each event fundamentally unpredictable by any physical theory.

The distinction between quantum randomness and classical randomness matters for the conceptual integrity of this work. A hardware TRNG derives entropy from thermal noise, which is in principle a classical process governed by statistical mechanics. Quantum vacuum fluctuations are fundamentally different: their randomness is not a consequence of ignorance about hidden variables but an intrinsic property of the quantum field. Bell's theorem [13] and decades of experimental verification, from Aspect's 1982 experiments [12] through the 2022 Nobel Prize winning work [14], establish that no local hidden variable theory can reproduce quantum measurement statistics.

C. Entropy Architecture

Each cat generation consumes one 256-byte block from a pre fetched entropy file on the SD card. Bytes 0 through 199 provide 100 Box Muller pairs for z-vector construction. Byte 200 determines the motivational state via a single quantum bit and bytes 202 through 205 select phrase components. The z-vector is constructed via Box Muller transform from pairs of uniform bytes, producing 100 independent samples from $N(0,1)$. A generation counter persisted to SD card ensures each power cycle advances to the next unused entropy block.

The question of whether stored random bytes retain their quantum character is worth addressing. The randomness was established at the moment of measurement. Storage does not change provenance. What it sacrifices is secrecy, which is irrelevant for a generative art installation. The system requires that each cat traces to a genuine quantum event, and that property is invariant under storage.

D. Phrase Synthesis and Audio

The spoken phrase is assembled combinatorially from four slots, each with 16 options across two banks (motivated and demotivated), producing 131,072 unique phrases. Each slot entry exists as a pre generated WAV clip on the SD card, generated using a neural text to speech engine and converted to 22050 Hz 16-bit mono PCM. The MCU plays four clips sequentially through the 12-bit DAC with a timer driven ring buffer. The total audio corpus is 128 WAV files occupying approximately 13 MB.

E. Wavefunction Collapse as User Interface

The boot sequence is designed around the superposition metaphor. After hardware initialization, both MOTIVATED and DEMOTIVATED labels are displayed simultaneously with alternating highlights that slow progressively before collapsing. During generation, the display shows the quantum seed bytes in hexadecimal, z vector values with their source byte pairs, and the active network layer. After generation, a provenance section shows the source bytes with attribution to the ANU measurement number and origin.

Fig. 2. TinyGAN running on the CH32H417 dual core RISC-V microcontroller. The 64x64 generated image is displayed at 3x nearest neighbor upscale (192x192) on a 480x320 LCD with quantum provenance data and motivational verdict.

F. Provenance and Irreproducibility

Every generated cat has a verifiable provenance chain: quantum vacuum fluctuations at ANU, balanced homodyne detection and digitization, API transmission and local storage, Box Muller transform to the latent vector, five-layer DCGAN forward pass, and pixel level image synthesis. No cat can be reproduced without the exact quantum bytes that produced it. The bytes cannot be predicted before measurement. Each cat is, in a strong and precise sense, unique.

VIII. DISCUSSION

A. Bottleneck Analysis

At 26 seconds, the system is dominated by SD card SPI throughput. The 12.1 MB of int8 weights transfer at approximately 1 MB/s, setting a floor of roughly 12 seconds for weight data movement alone. The SDMMC 4-bit interface could theoretically provide 12.5 MB/s, reducing weight transfer time to approximately 1 second and total inference to an estimated 8 to 10 seconds.

B. Quantization Quality

Int8 per channel quantization produces no visible degradation at 64x64 resolution. The generated images maintain clear facial features, appropriate color distribution, and spatial coherence. The int8 quantized output was compared against float32 reference output across 100 z-vectors, with maximum per pixel deviation of 1 LSB. A quantitative FID evaluation is planned for follow up work.

C. On Quantum Entropy

A legitimate criticism is that a classical PRNG would produce statistically indistinguishable output. From a pure image quality perspective, this is correct. The value of quantum entropy in this system is not statistical but ontological. A PRNG is a deterministic function of its seed but quantum vacuum fluctuations occupy a categorically different position in that they are not merely unpredictable but fundamentally indeterminate. The project makes this physics tangible by connecting a specific pixel in a specific cat face to a specific vacuum fluctuation event in Canberra through a provenance chain that does not exist with a PRNG.

D. Applicability

The techniques presented are applicable to any feedforward generative architecture. Conditional GANs, pix2pix generators, and other single pass architectures could use the same weight streaming, tiling, and dual core strategy. Diffusion models would multiply inference time by the number of denoising steps, requiring approximately 9 minutes for a 20-step model at current performance.

E. Limitations

The 64x64 output resolution is low by modern standards, though sufficient for the target display at 3x upscaling. The 26 second generation time precludes interactive applications. The DCGAN architecture produces lower quality output than more

recent generative architectures. The Box Muller transform from 8-bit uniform values provides only 256 levels of input resolution per uniform variable. The audio playback uses blocking DAC writes rather than DMA. These are engineering constraints rather than fundamental limitations.

IX. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated that generative adversarial network image generation is feasible on resource constrained RISC-V microcontrollers. A DCGAN generator with 12.6 million parameters produces 64x64 RGB images in 26 seconds on a CH32H417 dual core RISC-V SOC with 512 KB shared SRAM, achieving a 9.3x speedup over the baseline through systematic optimization of compute offloading, weight quantization, memory management, and I/O pipelining.

Beyond the technical demonstration, we have constructed a complete autonomous system that bridges quantum physics and generative AI on a low-cost RISC-V embedded platform. Each generated cat face traces its existence to quantum vacuum fluctuations measured at the Australian National University, with combinatorial phrase synthesis and neural text to speech delivering the quantum verdict through a speaker. The dominant performance bottleneck is SD card SPI throughput, suggesting that future work should focus on storage interface optimization and further weight compression rather than compute acceleration.

This work establishes baseline performance data for generative neural network inference on RISC-V microcontrollers, opening a new direction in the TinyML design space.

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The DCGAN generator was trained on the AFHQ dataset. Quantum random numbers were provided by the Australian National University Quantum Random Number Generator. The CH32H417 is manufactured by WCH (Nanjing Qinheng Microelectronics). Neural text to speech audio was generated using Microsoft Edge TTS.

REFERENCES

[1] A. Radford, L. Metz, and S. Chintala, "Unsupervised representation learning with deep convolutional generative adversarial networks," arXiv:1511.06434, 2015.

[2] I. Goodfellow et al., "Generative adversarial nets," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2014.

[3] C. Banbury et al., "MLPerf Tiny Benchmark," in *Proc. NeurIPS Datasets and Benchmarks*, 2021.

[4] B. Jacob et al., "Quantization and training of neural networks for efficient integer arithmetic only inference," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, 2018.

[5] Y. Choi et al., "StarGAN: Unified generative adversarial networks for multi domain image to image translation," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, 2018.

[6] J. Lin et al., "MCUNet: Tiny deep learning on IoT devices," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2020.

[7] P. Warden and D. Situnayake, *TinyML: Machine Learning with TensorFlow Lite on Arduino and Ultra Low Power Microcontrollers*. O'Reilly Media, 2019.

[8] Australian National University, "ANU QRNG – Quantum random numbers," <https://qrng.anu.edu.au>, accessed 2026.

[9] cpldcpu (Tim), "Generative AI on a Microcontroller," Hackaday.io project 193478, 2023 to 2025.

[10] cpldcpu (Tim), "BitNetMCU: Neural networks with low-bit weights on low end 32-bit microcontrollers," GitHub, 2024.

[11] E. Schrodinger, "Die gegenwartige Situation in der Quantenmechanik," *Naturwissenschaften*, vol. 23, no. 48, pp. 807 to 812; no. 49, pp. 823 to 828; no. 50, pp. 844 to 849, 1935.

[12] A. Aspect, J. Dalibard, and G. Roger, "Experimental test of Bell's inequalities using time varying analyzers," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, vol. 49, no. 25, pp. 1804 to 1807, 1982.

[13] J. S. Bell, "On the Einstein Podolsky Rosen paradox," *Physics Physique Fizika*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 195 to 200, 1964.

[14] Nobel Prize in Physics 2022, "For experiments with entangled photons, establishing the violation of Bell inequalities," NobelPrize.org, 2022.